

1 **Annual versus Biennial Kidding in Dairy Goats**

2 **Interpretive Summary:** Salama et al

3 A traditional 12-mo kidding interval was compared to a 24-mo kidding interval for effects on
4 lactation yields in dairy goats, and particularly, the impact of pregnancy on lactation. Losses
5 in milk yield started from the second month of pregnancy onwards. Goats kidding at 2-yr
6 intervals were as productive as goats kidding annually and their milk contained greater fat and
7 protein in the second year of lactation. Extended lactation seems to be a good strategy to
8 simplify management conditions and reduce animal stress related to negative energy balance
9 in early lactation.

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11 PREGNANCY AND EXTENDED LACTATION IN GOATS

12

13 **Effect of Pregnancy and Extended Lactation on Milk Production and**
14 **Udder Compartments in Dairy Goats Milked Once Daily**

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ABSTRACT

22
23 Thirty multiparous Murciano-Granadina dairy goats milked once daily were used to study
24 the lactational effects of an extended 24-mo kidding interval (K24; n = 14) compared to the
25 traditional 12-mo kidding interval (K12; n = 16). Goats were divided into 2 balanced groups
26 at wk 29 of lactation with respect to parity, milk yield, and SCC. Over a period of 92 wk, K12
27 goats were mated twice at wk 29 during the first lactation and at wk 79 during the second
28 lactation, whereas K24 goats were mated once at wk 79 of extended first lactation. The K12
29 goats were dried off from wk 14 to 21 of pregnancy (wk 43 to 50 of lactation). Milk yield was
30 recorded from wk 2 to 92, whereas milk composition was studied from wk 29 to 92. Milk
31 fatty acids were analyzed in milk samples taken at wk 39 (wk 10 of pregnancy) and 55 (wk 5
32 of subsequent lactation), when milk in udder compartments (cisternal and alveolar) was also
33 evaluated. Average milk yield during the first 29 wk was 2.23 ± 0.13 L/d. Pregnancy reduced
34 milk yield in K12 goats from wk 39 to 42 of lactation compared to K24 goats. During the dry
35 period for K12 goats, milk yield of K24 goats averaged 1.53 ± 0.10 L/d. From wk 51 to 79,
36 K12 goats produced 32% more milk than K24 goats, but their milk contained lower fat and
37 protein than K24 goats. No changes were detected for milk lactose and SCC from wk 51 to
38 79. From wk 80 to 92, differences in milk yield and milk composition between groups were
39 not significant. Milk of pregnant K12 goats contained higher C_{16:1} and conjugated C_{18:2} fatty
40 acids, and had a higher desaturase index than milk of open K24 goats at wk 39. In the
41 following lactation (wk 55), milk of K12 goats contained higher C_{18:2} and C_{18:3}, and lower
42 C_{16:0} fatty acids, resulting in a lower atherogenicity index compared to K24 goats. Cisternal
43 milk at wk 39 was lower for K12 than K24 goats, whereas alveolar milk did not differ. In K12
44 goats, values of cisternal milk tripled, but alveolar milk only doubled at wk 55 (wk 5 of
45 subsequent lactation) compared to wk 39, indicating the importance of the cistern in
46 accommodating high milk yield at early lactation. Values of cisternal and alveolar milk did

47 not differ between wk 39 and 55 for K24 goats. Fat content was higher for alveolar milk than
48 cisternal milk for K12 goats at wk 55 and for K24 goats at wk 39 and 55. No differences in
49 milk protein or lactose were detected between cisternal and alveolar milk. In conclusion,
50 pregnancy reduced milk yield from wk 10 after conceiving onwards. Extended lactation did
51 not significantly decrease milk yield (-8.2%), but increased milk components that may
52 contribute to cheese yield, and may be a useful strategy for reducing metabolic stress in early
53 lactation and for simplifying herd management in dairy goats.

54

55 **(Key Words:** pregnancy, extended lactation, cisternal and alveolar milk, dairy goat)

56 **Abbreviation key:** CLA = conjugated linoleic acid, FA = fatty acids, K12 = 12-mo kidding
57 interval, K24 = 24-mo kidding interval, TJ = tight junctions.

58

59

INTRODUCTION

60 Pregnancy has been shown to cause a significant decline in milk yield of dairy cows due to
61 hormonal changes (Bachman et al., 1988; Akers, 2002) and the nutritive requirements of the
62 fetus, especially during the third part of gestation (Bell et al., 1995). Some authors (Olori et
63 al., 1997; Brotherstone et al., 2004) reported milk yield losses in dairy cows from 5 mo of
64 pregnancy onwards, whereas other authors (Bormann et al., 2002) reported an earlier decline.
65 In the only available report on lactational effects of pregnancy in dairy goats mated at peak of
66 lactation (Knight and Wilde, 1988), milk yield decreased at the same rate in pregnant goats
67 during the first 8 wk of pregnancy as in non-pregnant goats. Nevertheless, milk yield
68 decreased more quickly in the pregnant goats thereafter, reaching 57% of the milk yield of
69 non-pregnant goats in the last wk before parturition. No information on the effects of
70 pregnancy on milk composition and milk partitioning in the udder was reported in the study of

71 Knight and Wilde (1988). Moreover, the impact of pregnancy on milk production in late
72 lactation (as in the case of dairy cows) has not been reported before in goats.

73 Extended lactation in dairy cows is an alternative to typical 300-DIM lactation. It reduces
74 the number of dry days within the animal's lifetime and the metabolic stress related to
75 negative energy balance during early lactation (Knight, 1997), and may be profitable for dairy
76 farmers (Arbel et al., 2001). Linzell (1973) observed that well fed non-pregnant goats, milked
77 twice daily, can lactate continuously for 2 to 4 yr. There is no information on the quality of
78 milk produced from goats under extended lactation.

79 The objective of this study was to investigate the lactational effects of 2 different kidding
80 intervals, producing a typical 12-mo lactation cycle in contrast to an extended lactation cycle
81 of 24 mo in Murciano-Granadina dairy goats milked once daily. Effects of pregnancy on
82 lactation were also evaluated.

83

84 **MATERIALS AND METHODS**

85 The experimental procedures and animal care conditions were approved by the Ethical
86 Committee of Animal and Human Experimentation of the Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona
87 (reference CEEAH 02/400).

88

89 **Animals and Management Conditions**

90 Thirty multiparous Murciano-Granadina dairy goats located on the experimental farm of the
91 SIGCE (Servei de Granges i Camps Experimentals) of the Universitat Autònoma de
92 Barcelona in Bellaterra were used after fall kidding (second week of October) with a litter size
93 of 2.12 ± 0.15 kids/goat. Murciano-Granadina goats are usually bred for an annual kidding
94 and have a wide reproduction season in Spain (Falagan, 1988), with a shallow seasonal

95 anestrus from February to June, and frequent out of season kidding for producing Christmas
96 milk kid ('cabrito lechal').

97 Goats were divided into 2 balanced groups at wk 29 of lactation with respect to parity, milk
98 yield (recorded from wk 2 to 29), and SCC (recorded on 2 consecutive d in wk 29). The
99 groups were: traditional 12-mo kidding interval (**K12**; n = 16), where goats were impregnated
100 twice at wk 29 and 79 of the study and dried off twice from wk 43 to 50 following first
101 lactation and from wk 93 to 100 after the second lactation; and extended 24-mo kidding
102 interval (**K24**; n = 14), where goats were impregnated once at wk 79 and dried off once from
103 wk 93 to 100. The average litter size in the previous kidding was 2.12 ± 0.15 and 2.23 ± 0.20
104 kids/goat for the goats in K12 and K24 groups, respectively. Mating was carried out in April
105 at wk 29 and 79 after natural induction of estrus by the buck effect without light treatment. A
106 teaser buck was introduced for 4 d and then replaced by a fertile one that impregnated 82% of
107 goats between d 5 and 9 of introduction.

108 During a 2-yr period, K12 goats had 2 lactations (from wk 1 to 42 and from wk 51 to 92),
109 whereas K24 goats had 1 extended lactation (from wk 1 to wk 92). The period from wk 30 to
110 wk 42 allowed us to study the effect of pregnancy on milk production in K12 pregnant goats
111 compared to K24 open goats.

112 Goats grazed [during 6 h/d in an annual Italian ryegrass prairie](#) and were supplemented in
113 the shelter with 0.5 to 1.0 kg/d of a commercial concentrate (1.53 Mcal NE_L/kg; 16% CP, as
114 fed) according to lactation stage, and with 0.5 kg/d alfalfa pellets. During the dry period (wk
115 43 to 50), goats were kept in pens and their individual daily ration consisted of a dehydrated
116 mixture of whole-plant corn and alfalfa hay (1:1) fed ad libitum, 0.2 kg whole barley grain,
117 0.3 kg alfalfa pellets, and 0.5 kg concentrate pellets.

118 Goats were milked once daily at 0900 h in a double-12 stall Casse system parallel milking
119 parlor (Westfalia-Surge Ibérica, Granollers, Spain) with recording jars ($2 \text{ L} \pm 5\%$) and low

120 milk pipeline. Typical milking settings were used (vacuum, 42 kPa; pulsation rate, 90
121 pulses/min; and pulsation ratio, 66%) for goats of this breed (Salama et al., 2004). Milking
122 routine included machine milking without udder preparation or teat cleaning, machine
123 stripping, and teat dipping in an iodine solution (P3-cide plus, Henkel Hygiene, Barcelona,
124 Spain).

125

126 **Procedures, Sample Collection and Analysis**

127 Milk yields of individual goats were recorded weekly by using the recording jars in the
128 milking parlor throughout the experiment. Milk composition and SCC were recorded
129 biweekly from wk 29 to 41 and monthly thereafter. A sample of approximately 50 mL was
130 placed in a plastic vial, preserved with an anti-microbial tablet (Bronopol, Broad Spectrum
131 Micro-tabs II, D&F Control Systems Inc., San Ramon, CA) and kept at 4°C until analysis.
132 Milk fat, protein, lactose and SCC were determined in the Dairy Herd Improvement
133 laboratory of Catalonia (Allic, Cabrils, Barcelona, Spain) using infrared spectroscopy and an
134 automated somatic cell counter (MilkoScan 4000 + Fossomatic 5000, Foss-Electric, Hillerød,
135 Denmark).

136 During wk 39 and 55 (wk 10 of pregnancy and wk 5 of the subsequent lactation,
137 respectively for K12 goats), a 50 mL milk sample from K12 and K24 goats was collected,
138 immediately cooled, and the fat fraction was separated by centrifugation for 30 min at 6000 ×
139 g and 4°C and then stored at -80°C. Methylation of fatty acids (FA) was performed according
140 to Sukhija and Palmquist (1988) and the modifications of Kramer et al. (1997). Fatty acid
141 methyl esters were analyzed by gas chromatography (HP 6890, Agilent Technologies, Palo
142 Alto, CA) equipped with a flame ionization detector and HP-23 (cis/trans FAME) capillary
143 column (60 m × 0.25 mm i.d. with 0.25-µm film thickness; Agilent Technologies, Palo Alto,
144 CA). Initial temperature was 40°C (for 6 min) increased to 230°C (for 12 min) at a rate of

145 5°C/min. Individual FA were identified by comparison of retention times to those of pure
146 standards (Sigma-Aldrich Química, Madrid, Spain) and expressed as percentages of the total
147 FA detected as fatty acid methyl esters.

148 Milk partitioning in the udder (cisternal and alveolar) of K12 and K24 goats was
149 determined at wk 39 and 55. To prevent undesired milk letdown during evaluation of milk
150 partitioning in the udder, each goat received 0.8 mg (i.v.) of Atosiban (Tractocile, Ferring,
151 Spain), an oxytocin receptor blocking agent, while in their pens (Salama et al., 2004).
152 Thereafter, goats were taken to the milking parlor and machine milked to evacuate cisternal
153 milk. Approximately 20 min after the Atosiban injection, goats received 2 IU (i.v.) of
154 oxytocin (Laboratorios Ovejero, León, Spain) and machine-milked to obtain the letdown
155 alveolar milk. Samples of cisternal and alveolar milk were taken for the analysis of fat,
156 protein, lactose and SCC as previously described.

157

158 **Statistical Analyses**

159 Data were analyzed by ANOVA using the PROC MIXED for repeated measurements (SAS
160 Inst., Inc., Cary, NC, Version 8.2). The statistical mixed model contained the fixed effects of
161 treatment (K12 or K24), wk of lactation and parity, the random effect of animal within
162 treatment, the interactions between treatment and week of lactation and between treatment and
163 parity, and the residual error. For data analyses of milk fractions composition, the fixed effect
164 of fraction (cisternal or alveolar) and the triple interaction for treatment, week of lactation,
165 and fraction were added to the model. Logarithmic transformations (\log_{10}) of SCC values
166 were used in the statistical analyses.

167

168 **RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

169 **Milk Yield**

170 Average data of milk yield and milk composition, and milk yield changes throughout the
171 experiment (92 wk) are shown in Table 1 and Figure 1. Milk yield before conception (wk 2 to
172 29 of lactation) and during the first 7 wk of pregnancy (wk 30 to 36 of lactation) was similar
173 for K12 and K24 goats and averaged 2.15 ± 0.14 L/d. Milk yield of K12 goats tended to be
174 lower than K24 goats at wk 8 (1.52 ± 0.14 vs. 1.80 ± 0.18 L/d; $P = 0.068$) and wk 9 ($1.38 \pm$
175 0.14 vs. 1.65 ± 0.18 L/d; $P = 0.114$) of pregnancy. However, the impact of pregnancy started
176 to be significant ($P < 0.05$) in K12 goats at wk 10 of pregnancy (wk 39 of lactation). Milk
177 yield losses were 0.32 ($P < 0.05$), 0.51 ($P < 0.001$), 0.85 ($P < 0.001$) and 1.11 ($P < 0.001$) L/d
178 at wk 10, 11, 12, and 13 of pregnancy, respectively, representing approximately a 1.5-fold
179 increase in the rate of decline each week over that period. Knight and Wilde (1988) reported
180 that pregnancy had no effect on milk yield during the first 8 wk of pregnancy in Saanen goats,
181 but milk yield decreased rapidly thereafter and was 57% of the value of non-pregnant goats in
182 the last wk of pregnancy. Milk yield in K12 goats at wk 13 of pregnancy (wk 42 of lactation)
183 was only 21% of the value of K24 goats (0.31 ± 0.09 vs. 1.41 ± 0.14 L/d; $P < 0.001$). In our
184 experiment, goats were milked once daily and mated relatively late in lactation (wk 29),
185 which might explain the greater milk yield losses compared to the experiment of Knight and
186 Wilde (1988) where goats were milked twice daily and mated much earlier than in our study
187 (wk 8). The greater effect of pregnancy on late lactation may be due to the decreasing power
188 of galactopoietic hormones as lactation advanced. Sorensen and Knight (2002) reported that
189 blood concentration of GH decreased whereas insulin concentration increased, as lactation
190 advanced in dairy cows. Pregnancy also caused a significant decline in milk yield of dairy
191 cows in late lactation from mo 5 of gestation onwards (Olori et al., 1997; Brotherstone et al.,
192 2004) or from as early as mo 3 of pregnancy (Bormann et al., 2002).

193 The mechanism by which pregnancy influences milk yield is not fully understood, but it is
194 believed to be caused by the hormones released during pregnancy, most probably estrogen

195 (Bachman et al., 1988; Akers, 2002). Administration of estrogen caused mammary gland
196 regression with a significant decline in milk yield in lactating goats (Peaker and Linzell,
197 1974). Moreover, estradiol injection before drying off accelerated mammary tissue involution
198 in dairy cows (Athie et al., 1997) and goats (Mellado et al., 1998) by promoting plasminogen
199 activation (Athie et al., 1997). Circulating estradiol is low until wk 9 of pregnancy in goats,
200 increases gradually until 1 wk before kidding, and then peaks before kidding (Dhindsa et al.,
201 1981). Estradiol concentration during pregnancy is proportional to the number of fetuses
202 (Dhindsa et al., 1981; Manalu et al., 1996). Litter size in K12 goats averaged 2.2 ± 0.1
203 kids/goat, which is relatively high for goats (Amoah et al., 1996), indicating that a marked
204 effect of estrogen on milk secretion must have occurred. Beside the estrogen, placental
205 lactogen peaks during the last third of pregnancy and may influence mammogenesis and
206 lactogenesis, and alter the maternal metabolism in order to accommodate the growth and
207 development of the fetus (Akers, 2002).

208 In addition to the hormonal effect, yield losses might be due to the nutritive requirements of
209 the gravid uterus. Energy requirements for pregnancy do not only include the energy
210 deposited in the conceptus, but also the energy used for the conceptus metabolism and the
211 energy used by maternal tissues to support the conceptus (Freetly and Ferrell, 1998). In the
212 current study, we found a negative correlation ($R^2 = 0.35$; $P < 0.05$) between litter birth
213 weight and milk yield at wk 13 of pregnancy (wk 42 of lactation) before drying off (data not
214 shown), which may indicate the competition for energy between milk production and
215 conceptus. Glucose is the main source of energy for the gravid uterus, and an increase in the
216 net hepatic plasma glucose release in pregnant ewes has been reported from d 40 of pregnancy
217 onwards (Freetly and Ferrell, 1998). Despite this hepatic release of glucose, pregnant goats
218 had lower concentrations of blood glucose than the non-pregnant goats after d 84 of
219 pregnancy (Khan and Lurdi, 2002). This suggests that there may be a competition for glucose

220 between the mammary gland (for lactose synthesis) and the gravid uterus (especially with
221 twins or triplets), which would result in milk yield losses during pregnancy.

222 From wk 43 to 50, K12 goats were dried off whereas K24 goats produced 1.53 ± 0.10 L/d
223 (Table 1 and Figure 1). From wk 51 to 92, milk yield of K12 goats peaked (2.67 ± 0.15 L/d)
224 between wk 53 and 55 (wk 3 and 5 of subsequent lactation) and then descended gradually (P
225 < 0.05), while milk yield in K24 goats tended ($P < 0.10$) to increase at wk 68 of lactation from
226 1.43 ± 0.14 to 1.65 ± 0.16 L/d (Figure 1). This increase in milk yield of K24 goats was
227 maintained throughout spring when grass quality and photoperiod are increasing. A longer
228 photoperiod is related to increases in circulating prolactin in goats (Kornalijnslijper et al.,
229 1997), and prolactin and IGF-I in dairy cows (Dahl and Petitclerc, 2003). In accordance with
230 our results, non-pregnant goats continued to lactate for 2 to 4 yr and had a rise in milk yield in
231 the spring either when they were grazing (Mackenzie, 1967) or when they were kept housed
232 under constant values of light and temperature and given dry feeds (Linzell, 1973). It is not
233 clear why the positive effect of longer daylight was more evident in K24 goats than in K12
234 goats. From wk 51 to 79 (wk 1 to 29 of subsequent lactation), K12 goats produced 32% more
235 milk ($P < 0.001$) than K24 goats; this difference decreased to 28% when milk yield was
236 corrected for fat content, but the difference was still significant ($P < 0.01$) as shown in Table
237 1. Differences in milk yield between groups were maintained until wk 85 and were
238 insignificant thereafter (Figure 1). Nevertheless, from wk 80 to 92 (wk 30 to 42 of subsequent
239 lactation), no differences were detected between K12 and K24 goats for milk yield ($P =$
240 0.151) and FCM (Table 1).

241 In the 92-wk experimental period, K12 and K24 goats produced a similar total milk yield
242 (1192 ± 58 L and 1093 ± 73 L; for K12 and K24, respectively; $P = 0.319$). No significant
243 losses in milk yield were reported either in dairy cows when the calving interval was extended
244 from 12 to 14 (Arbel et al., 2001), or 16 mo (Osterman and Bertilsson, 2003). The K24 goats

245 lost the kid crop of 1 yr. The reduced income in K24 goats was partially compensated by the
246 greater price of the milk produced between wk 51 and 79 which was richer in fat and protein
247 than in K12 goats (Table 1). Moreover, the biennial kidding system with extended lactation
248 may be a good alternative for goats that remain open after mating in the first year and those
249 could be remated with their counterparts in the second year.

250 Goats were mated at wk 79 (wk 29 of subsequent lactation) and all became pregnant and
251 kidded at $d 158 \pm 1.9$ d after the start of mating, indicating that both goat groups were in
252 adequate condition for reproduction. Similarly, Ratnayake et al. (1998) reported no
253 differences in fertility among dairy cows managed for calving intervals of 12, 15, or 18 mo.

254

255 **Milk Composition and SCC**

256 Values of milk fat, protein, lactose, and \log_{10} SCC did not differ between K12 and K24
257 goats from wk 30 to 38 of lactation (Table 1). However, differences were detected at wk 41
258 (wk 12 of pregnancy), when milk yield of K12 goats was low and tended to contain more fat
259 (4.63 ± 0.18 vs. $3.86 \pm 0.21\%$; $P < 0.10$), more protein (4.89 ± 0.16 vs. $3.43 \pm 0.19\%$; $P <$
260 0.001), and less lactose (3.58 ± 0.10 vs. $4.23 \pm 0.12\%$; $P < 0.001$) than milk from K24 goats
261 (Figure 2). Leakiness of tight junctions (**TJ**) at advanced pregnancy may account for milk
262 composition differences between K12 and K24 goats. Elevated levels of progesterone induce
263 TJ leakiness and the injection of a progesterone antagonist in mice in late pregnancy resulted
264 in a rapid closure of TJ (Nguyen et al., 2001). The highest level of circulating progesterone
265 was reported to be between wk 8 (when placenta is functional) and wk 17 of pregnancy in
266 goats (Kornalijnslijper et al., 1997), and was proportional to the number of fetuses (Manalu et
267 al., 1996). Thus, elevated progesterone concentrations during advanced pregnancy may favor
268 TJ leakiness.

269 Comparing wk 2 and 12 of pregnancy (wk 31 and 41 of lactation), increases ($P < 0.001$) in
270 milk fat (4.32 ± 0.13 to $4.63 \pm 0.20\%$), milk protein (3.21 ± 0.08 to $4.89 \pm 0.28\%$) and \log_{10}
271 SCC (5.98 ± 0.08 to 6.55 ± 0.11) were detected in K12 goats, whereas milk lactose decreased
272 ($P < 0.001$) from 4.51 ± 0.03 to $3.58 \pm 0.15\%$ (Figure 2). Similarly, increases in milk fat and
273 protein contents, and a decrease in lactose content were observed in dairy cows in late
274 pregnancy at the end of lactation (Remond et al., 1992; Olori et al., 1997). Changes in milk
275 composition before drying off in K12 goats may be the result of TJ leakiness, thus reducing
276 milk secretion and allowing the flow of plasma proteins into the alveolar lumen (Nguyen et
277 al., 2001). Leaky TJ may also result in lactose loss from milk to plasma (Stelwagen et al.,
278 1995), which may explain the low content of milk lactose at wk 12 of pregnancy.

279 During the first 29 wk of the subsequent lactation (wk 51 to 79), milk from K12 goats
280 contained less ($P < 0.05$) fat (-14%) and protein (-10%) than milk from K24 goats (Table 1
281 and Figure 2). The lower fat and protein contents in milk of K12 goats is probably due to a
282 dilution effect as their milk yield was greater than K24 goats. Moreover, the negative energy
283 balance at early lactation in K12 goats (see below) could lead to a lower percentage of protein
284 as previously reported in dairy cows (Remond et al., 1992). From wk 51 to 79 (wk 1 to 29 of
285 subsequent lactation), no differences ($P > 0.10$) between groups were detected for milk
286 lactose and SCC (Table 1 and Figure 2). Lactose is the major osmotic regulator of milk, and a
287 strong positive correlation exists between lactose synthesis and milk yield. Knight and Wilde
288 (1993) found that the number of secretory cells in the udder of goats decreased as lactation
289 advanced, but cell activity remained unchanged. Reduced milk yield without reduced lactose
290 content in K24 goats suggests a lower number of secretory cells in the udder of K24 goats.

291 During pregnancy in the subsequent lactation (wk 80 to 92), milk composition and SCC did
292 not differ between groups on average: fat, $4.85 \pm 0.24\%$; protein, $3.97 \pm 0.13\%$; lactose, 4.13
293 $\pm 0.06\%$; and \log_{10} SCC, 6.32 ± 0.10 .

294 Throughout the study, milk SCC exceeded the limit of 1×10^6 cells/ml except for K12 at
295 wk 52 (wk 2 of subsequent lactation). The SCC values were slightly higher than those
296 previously reported by Salama et al. (2003) in the same breed milked once daily. This greater
297 content of SCC seems to be due to a parity effect rather than an effect of once-daily milking.
298 All goats in the current study were multiparous, and Salama et al. (2003) reported an increase
299 in milk SCC as parity number increased, with no difference in SCC between goats milked
300 once- or twice-daily.

301

302 **Fatty Acid Profile of Milk Fat**

303 Only minor differences in FA profile were observed between K12 and K24 goats at wk 39
304 (wk 10 of pregnancy), when milk fat of K12 goats contained greater ($P < 0.05$) palmitoleic
305 ($C_{16:1}$) and the *cis*-9, *trans*-11 isomer of conjugated linoleic acid (CLA) than K24 goats (Table
306 2). The CLA ($C_{18:2}$ *cis*-9, *trans*-11) is synthesized in the rumen and is also produced in the
307 mammary gland by Δ^9 -desaturase enzyme, and its increase in dairy products is considered to
308 be desirable (McGuire and McGuire, 1999). An increase ($P < 0.05$) in the $C_{16:1}/C_{16:0}$ and
309 $C_{18:1}/C_{18:0}$ desaturase indices, related to the activity of the Δ^9 -desaturase enzyme (Perfield et
310 al., 2002; Kelsey et al., 2003), was observed in the milk of K12 goats compared to K24 goats
311 (Table 2). Consequently, the CLA content in milk of K12 goats was 18.2 % greater ($P < 0.05$)
312 than that of K24 goats but only at wk 39.

313 At wk 55 (wk 5 of subsequent lactation) more FA differences between groups were
314 observed ($P < 0.05$). Thus, milk fat from K12 goats contained higher levels of caproic ($C_{6:0}$),
315 caprylic ($C_{8:0}$), capric ($C_{10:0}$), margaric ($C_{17:0}$), linoleic ($C_{18:2}$), and linolenic ($C_{18:3}$), and lower
316 palmitic ($C_{16:0}$) and $C_{16:1}$ than K24 goats (Table 2). The effect was more marked in $C_{16:0}$
317 (17.5%) that correlates negatively with C4 to C8 (Chilliard et al., 2003), agreeing with the
318 greater percentages of these short chain FA in the milk of K12 goats at wk 55. Human diets

319 rich in C_{12:0}, C_{14:0} and C_{16:0} FA are potentially hypercholesterolic, whereas, C_{18:0} and
320 unsaturated long chain FA have cholesterol lowering and anti-atherogenic properties (Ney,
321 1991). In our results, the atherogenicity index in K12 was lower ($P < 0.05$) than K24 at wk 55
322 (wk 5 of subsequent lactation) when C_{16:0} percentages were low and polyunsaturated FA (C_{18:2}
323 and C_{18:3}) were high (Table 2).

324 Stage of lactation markedly affected the FA profile of milk fat in K12 goats as previously
325 reported by Schmidely et al. (2002). Milk fat of K12 goats at wk 39 (wk 10 of pregnancy) or
326 in late lactation contained greater ($P < 0.05$) percentages of myristic (C_{14:0}), pentadecanoic
327 (C_{15:0}), C_{16:0} and C_{16:1}, and lower ($P < 0.05$) C_{6:0}, C_{8:0}, C_{10:0}, C_{17:0}, stearic (C_{18:0}), C_{18:2}, and
328 C_{18:3} acids than milk fat at wk 55 (wk 5 of subsequent lactation) or in early lactation. The
329 greater long chain FA (C18) percentages at wk 55 (wk 5 of subsequent lactation) could be a
330 consequence of the mobilization of body reserves during the negative energy balance in early
331 lactation, as indicated previously during early lactation in dairy goats (Schmidely et al., 2002).
332 Negative correlation exists between C18 and medium-chain FA in milk fat of dairy goats
333 (Chilliard et al., 2003) as found in our results for the same FA in the milk of K12 goats at wk
334 5 of the subsequent lactation (Table 2). The CLA concentration in milk fat of K12 was greater
335 ($P < 0.05$) at wk 39 than at wk 55 agreeing with the greater desaturase activity observed at wk
336 39. Moreover, the secretion of polyunsaturated FA, known as inhibitors of desaturase activity
337 (Chilliard et al., 2003), was lowest ($P < 0.05$) at wk 39 in K12 goats. We are not aware of any
338 previous research on the effect of lactation stage on CLA or desaturase index in goat milk.
339 Similar to our results, a small, but significant increase in milk fat content of CLA and
340 desaturase index as lactation advanced was reported in dairy cows (Kelsey et al., 2003), but
341 Stanton et al. (1997) found no effect of lactation stage on milk fat CLA levels in dairy cows.

342 On the contrary, the FA concentrations of milk fat in K24 goats were unchanged between
343 wk 39 and 55 except for pentadecanoic (C_{15:0}) acid, which was greater ($P < 0.05$) at wk 39

344 (Table 2). This may be a consequence of the unchanged physiological stage during extended
345 lactation, and of the steady state of nutrition despite probable seasonal changes in the quality
346 of pasture.

347

348 **Milk Fractions in the Udder**

349 *Yield of milk fractions.* Figure 3 shows milk partitioning and milk accumulation rates in the
350 alveolar and cisternal udder compartments in K12 and K24 goats. Percentages of cisternal
351 milk varied according to lactation wk (58 to 82%) and agreed with values previously reported
352 in Murciano-Granadina dairy goats (Salama et al., 2004).

353 At wk 39 (wk 10 of pregnancy), K12 goats had lower ($P < 0.05$) total milk (975 ± 167 vs.
354 1912 ± 270 mL), cisternal milk (638 ± 126 vs. 1560 ± 214 mL) and percentage of cisternal
355 milk (57.7 ± 4.0 vs. 82.1 ± 6.2 %) than K24 open goats. Nevertheless, volume of alveolar
356 milk was similar for K12 and K24 goats and averaged 345 ± 78 mL.

357 At wk 55 (wk 5 of subsequent lactation), milk yield of K12 goats peaked after kidding and
358 the volume of cisternal milk tripled ($P < 0.001$) its value at wk 39, whereas volume of
359 alveolar milk only doubled ($P < 0.001$) as shown in Figure 3. Volumes of cisternal and
360 alveolar milk at wk 55 in K12 goats were greater ($P < 0.01$) than in K24 goats, without
361 differences in cisternal milk percentages. In contrast to K12 goats, K24 goats were in a similar
362 physiological stage between wk 39 and 55 and their milk yields remained similar across that
363 period; thereby volumes of cisternal and alveolar milk, as well as cisternal milk percentages,
364 remained unchanged. These results indicate the main role of the cistern for accommodating
365 the udder to changes in milk yield (i.e. K12 goats at early lactation). This conclusion is also
366 supported by the fact that milk accumulation rates were less marked in the alveolar than in the
367 cisternal compartment for both goat groups (Figure 3). Expected differences in cisternal milk

368 between groups should be lower with twice-daily milking, according to the results obtained by
369 Salama et al. (2004) in the same breed.

370 With regard to the effects of stage of lactation on udder compartments, lower ($P < 0.001$)
371 volume and percentage of cisternal milk were observed in K12 goats in late lactation when
372 compared to their own values in early lactation (Figure 3). Although no data were available on
373 volume and percentage of cisternal milk in K24 goats in early lactation, a reduction in this
374 udder compartment was expected as milk yield decreased. Caja et al. (2004) reported in dairy
375 cows that volume of cisternal milk decreased, while its proportion increased, as lactation
376 advanced. The difference between goats and cows could be due to the larger cisternal
377 compartment in goats compared to cows, as indicated by Salama et al. (2004). The effect of
378 pregnancy on cisternal milk volume was attributed to a decrease in the nutrients available for
379 milk synthesis, as discussed above, resulting in a decrease in milk yield.

380 **Composition of milk fractions.** No references are available on the composition of alveolar
381 and cisternal milk fractions in dairy goats. Alveolar milk contained greater ($P < 0.001$) fat
382 than cisternal milk, except for K12 goats at wk 39 (wk 10 of pregnancy) when milk yield was
383 very low (Table 3). Similar results were reported in dairy cows (Ayadi et al., 2004) and ewes
384 (McKusick et al., 2002). Milk fat globules are large and do not pass freely from alveoli to
385 cistern, and therefore more fat is retained in the alveolar compartment (McKusick et al., 2002;
386 Ayadi et al., 2004). This emphasizes the importance of milk ejection and complete milking for
387 recovery of milk that is rich in fat.

388 No differences in protein and lactose content between cisternal and alveolar milk were
389 observed (Table 3). Differences between alveolar and cisternal concentrations of milk protein
390 and lactose are minimal in dairy cows (Ayadi et al., 2004) and dairy ewes (McKusick et al.,
391 2002). Milk protein is found primarily in the form of small casein micelles (Cowie and
392 Tindal, 1971) and therefore could pass freely between alveolar and cisternal compartments

393 between milkings, resulting in minimal differences in protein concentrations of milk fractions.
394 Synthesis of protein and lactose is synergistic and regulated by a final shared metabolic
395 pathway (Fitzgerald et al., 1970), thus it is expected that both components change similarly.
396 Cisternal and alveolar SCC were similar for open and pregnant goats at wk 39 (Table 3).
397 However, cisternal SCC was lower ($P < 0.05$) than alveolar SCC at wk 55 (wk 5 of
398 subsequent lactation) for K12 goats. This result is consistent with lower SCC in foremilk
399 compared to stripped milk in dairy ewes (Peris et al., 1991) and dairy cows (Bruckmaier et al.,
400 2004). Nevertheless, Ontsouka et al. (2003) found no differences in SCC between milk
401 fractions in dairy cows. The difference between cisternal and alveolar SCC observed in early
402 lactating goats in our study reflects the importance of the methodology of milk sampling for
403 SCC determination. Usually, foremilk samples are taken for SCC determination and udder
404 health monitoring in dairy goats. Thus, these samples may not reflect the actual SCC in the
405 total milk at the end of milking.

406 407 **CONCLUSIONS**

408 Pregnancy caused a dramatic milk yield drop in dairy goats, which was observable from the
409 second month after mating, and facilitates drying off before the next kidding. When mating
410 was not done, goats machine milked once daily under semi-extensive conditions, lactated for
411 2 yr consecutively without significant losses in milk yield. Because milk of K24 goats
412 contained more fat and protein with no significant increase in SCC, reduced revenue due to
413 kid crop loss could be partially offset if payment for milk was based on milk quality.
414 Extended lactation may be a useful strategy for reducing goat stress throughout their lifespan
415 in compromised conditions due to high milk yield or low nutritive resources.

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553 **Table 1.** Lactational performances of dairy goats according to kidding interval and physiological stage during the 92-wk experimental period
 554 (data are least squares means \pm SE).

Item	Kidding interval, mo	wk 2 to 29 ¹	wk 30 to 38	wk 39 to 42	wk 43 to 50	wk 51 to 79 ¹	wk 80 to 92
Physiological stage	12	Open & lactating	— Pregnant & lactating —	— Dried off	Open & lactating	Pregnant & lactating	
	24	...	(wk 1 to 9) ²	(wk 10 to 13) ²	(wk 14 to 21) ²	...	(wk 1 to 12) ²
			Open & lactating				Pregnant & lactating
							(wk 1 to 12) ²
Goats, n	12	16	16	16	16	16	16
	24	14	14	14	14	14	14
Milk yield, L/d	12	2.24 \pm 0.12	1.79 \pm 0.14	0.81 ^b \pm 0.11	...	2.42 ^a \pm 0.12	1.55 \pm 0.10
	24	2.21 \pm 0.15	1.88 \pm 0.16	1.63 ^a \pm 0.14	1.53 \pm 0.10	1.65 ^b \pm 0.17	1.33 \pm 0.13
FCM ³ , L/d	12	...	1.90 \pm 0.13	0.84 ^b \pm 0.10	...	2.73 ^a \pm 0.14	1.66 \pm 0.15
	24	...	1.96 \pm 0.16	1.57 ^a \pm 0.12	1.59 \pm 0.10	1.96 ^b \pm 0.18	1.45 \pm 0.16
Milk fat, %	12	...	4.23 \pm 0.16	4.17 \pm 0.14	...	4.72 ^b \pm 0.14	4.68 \pm 0.24
	24	...	4.17 \pm 0.21	3.85 \pm 0.18	4.43 \pm 0.15	5.37 ^a \pm 0.19	5.02 \pm 0.25
Milk protein, %	12	...	3.30 \pm 0.10	4.22 ^a \pm 0.20	...	3.45 ^b \pm 0.10	3.97 \pm 0.13
	24	...	3.21 \pm 0.13	3.30 ^b \pm 0.24	3.52 \pm 0.10	3.81 ^a \pm 0.13	3.96 \pm 0.14
Milk lactose, %	12	...	4.45 \pm 0.05	3.81 ^b \pm 0.08	...	4.51 \pm 0.04	4.10 \pm 0.06
	24	...	4.34 \pm 0.07	4.15 ^a \pm 0.09	4.37 \pm 0.08	4.42 \pm 0.06	4.15 \pm 0.06
Milk SCC, log	12	...	6.08 \pm 0.11	6.51 \pm 0.14	...	6.10 \pm 0.10	6.34 \pm 0.10
	24	...	6.04 \pm 0.14	6.29 \pm 0.17	6.46 \pm 0.12	6.13 \pm 0.13	6.31 \pm 0.09

555
 556 ¹ Start of mating at wk 29 and 79.

557 ² Wk of pregnancy

558 ³ FCM = 0.4 (L of milk) + 15 (kg fat).

559 ^{a, b} Means with different superscripts within the same column for each variable are different ($P < 0.05$).

560 **Table 2.** Effect of kidding interval and lactation stage on fatty acid composition of milk fat in
 561 dairy goats (data are least squares means of percentages of total methyl esters).

Fatty acid	Kidding interval, mo				SEM
	12		24		
	wk 39 ¹	wk 55 ²	wk 39	wk 55	
Goats, n	16	16	14	14	
Fatty acid					
C _{4:0}	0.94	1.01	1.00	0.94	0.04
C _{6:0}	1.12 ^b	1.45 ^a	1.23 ^b	1.25 ^b	0.07
C _{8:0}	2.12 ^b	2.77 ^a	2.26 ^b	2.24 ^b	0.11
C _{10:0}	9.34 ^b	10.86 ^a	9.74 ^b	9.68 ^b	0.37
C _{10:1}	0.20	0.18	0.14	0.21	0.05
C _{12:0}	5.09	5.30	4.81	5.00	0.36
C _{14:0}	11.31 ^a	10.33 ^b	10.67 ^{ab}	10.76 ^{ab}	0.46
C _{15:0}	1.65 ^a	1.48 ^b	1.71 ^a	1.41 ^b	0.09
C _{16:0}	31.00 ^a	26.58 ^b	31.40 ^a	31.23 ^a	0.94
C _{16:1}	1.68 ^a	1.26 ^b	1.29 ^b	1.41 ^b	0.11
C _{17:0}	1.45 ^b	1.62 ^a	1.54 ^{ab}	1.40 ^b	0.07
C _{17:1}	0.30	0.33	0.30	0.31	0.02
C _{18:0}	7.37 ^b	9.47 ^a	8.42 ^{ab}	8.34 ^{ab}	0.63
C _{18:1}	20.05	20.33	19.27	19.52	0.87
C _{18:2}	2.45 ^b	2.95 ^a	2.49 ^b	2.49 ^b	0.11
C _{18:3}	1.14 ^b	1.43 ^a	1.30 ^{ab}	1.13 ^b	0.09
C _{18:2 cis-9, trans 11 (CLA)}	0.78 ^a	0.62 ^b	0.66 ^b	0.60 ^b	0.04
Desaturase index ³					
C _{16:1} /C _{16:0}	0.054 ^a	0.048 ^b	0.041 ^b	0.045 ^b	0.003
C _{18:1} /C _{18:0}	2.80 ^a	2.20 ^b	2.36 ^b	2.39 ^b	0.18
Atherogenicity index ⁴	3.12 ^a	2.76 ^b	3.16 ^a	3.13 ^a	0.16

562 ¹ wk 10 of pregnancy for 12-mo kidding interval.

563 ² wk 5 of the subsequent lactation.

564 ³ According to Perfield et al. (2002).

565 ⁴ (C12 + 4C14 + C16)/sum of unsaturated fatty acids (from Ulbricht and Southgate, 1991).

566 ^{a, b} Means with different superscripts within row differ ($P < 0.05$).

567

568 **Table 3.** Effect of kidding interval and lactation stage on composition of milk fractions in
 569 dairy goats (data are least squares means).

Item	Kidding interval, mo				SEM
	12		24		
	wk 39 ¹	wk 55 ²	wk 39	wk 55	
Goats, n	16	16	14	14	
Fat, %					
Cisternal	4.97 ^a	3.83 ^{bc,e}	3.02 ^{c,e}	4.38 ^{ab,e}	0.66
Alveolar	5.58 ^{bc}	7.36 ^{a,d}	5.01 ^{c,d}	6.18 ^{b,d}	0.65
SEM	0.48	0.45	0.54	0.55	-
Protein, %					
Cisternal	4.70 ^a	3.26 ^b	3.02 ^b	3.64 ^b	0.42
Alveolar	4.99 ^a	3.13 ^b	3.00 ^b	3.69 ^b	0.44
SEM	0.31	0.29	0.35	0.35	-
Lactose, %					
Cisternal	4.22 ^b	4.47 ^a	4.35 ^{ab}	4.28 ^{ab}	0.11
Alveolar	4.20 ^b	4.42 ^a	4.34 ^{ab}	4.33 ^{ab}	0.09
SEM	0.08	0.08	0.09	0.10	-
SCC, log ₁₀ /mL					
Cisternal	6.38 ^a	5.84 ^{b,d}	6.29 ^a	6.41 ^a	0.19
Alveolar	6.41 ^a	6.09 ^{b,e}	6.34 ^{ab}	6.47 ^a	0.19
SEM	0.13	0.12	0.15	0.15	-

570 ¹ wk 10 of pregnancy for 12-mo kidding interval.

571 ² wk 5 of the subsequent lactation.

572 ^{a, b, c} Means with different superscripts within row differ ($P < 0.05$).

573 ^{d, e} Means of cisternal and alveolar fractions with different superscripts within variables differ
 574 ($P < 0.05$).

575

576 **Figure 1.** Daily milk yield in dairy goats kidded annually (●) or biennially (○). Values are
 577 means with SE indicated by vertical bars.

578

579

580 **Figure 2.** Milk fat, protein, lactose and SCC in dairy goats kidded annually (●) or biennially

581 (○). Values are means with SE indicated by vertical bars.

582

583 **Figure 3.** Milk partitioning (upper panel) and milk accumulation rates (lower panel) in the
 584 udder of dairy goats kidded annually (K12) or biennially (K24). Measurements were carried
 585 out at wk 39 (wk 10 of pregnancy) and 55 (wk 5 of subsequent lactation) of lactation. Values
 586 are least squares means with SE indicated by vertical bars. Different means ($P < 0.05$) are
 587 indicated by different letters.

588

